

Popular Article

Agricultural Marketing in India: Challenges and Suggestions

Soham Bachaspati¹, Ayoushmoti Chakraborty²

¹ Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Agricultural Economics, Faculty of Agriculture, BCKV, Mohanpur, West Bengal, India, pin 743145

² M.Sc. Scholar, Department of Life Science, MAKAUT, West Bengal, India

Introduction

The term agricultural marketing consists of two major terms viz., agriculture and marketing. Agriculture deals with the production of food and related products with the help of natural and artificial factors. Market is a place where buyers and sellers assemble to buy and sell products at different price level. Agricultural marketing refers to all those processes which take place from taking the agricultural product from the farmers to the consumers. Agricultural marketing includes gathering the agricultural produces, their standardization and grading, their storage, sending them to the market through various middlemen, selling in the market and arranging the required finance, etc. There are different types of agricultural markets in India such as primary or local markets, secondary or wholesale markets or assembly markets, terminal markets or retail markets, fairs, regulated markets, cooperative markets and state markets.

Challenges

One of the major problems of agricultural marketing is the lack of proper storage and warehouses for farmers to store their produces. Every year 15 to 30 per cent of the agricultural produce are damaged either by rats or rains due to the absence of proper storage facilities. (1) Agricultural commodities being perishable in nature degrade in absence of proper storage facilities and the producer farmers incur heavy losses. Another major problem of agricultural marketing is distress sale. The farmers, of whom majority is poor, are forced to sell their produce at less price to local money lenders cum traders as their economic conditions do not permit the poor farmers to wait for better prices. In the absence of proper road transportation facilities in the rural areas, Indian farmers cannot reach nearby urban markets to sell their produce at a fair price. Thus, they prefer to sell their produce at the village markets itself in lesser price. The condition of the mandis are also not at all favorable to the farmers. In the mandis, the farmers have to wait for disposing their produce for which there is no storage facilities. Thus, the farmers are forced to take help of the middlemen who take away a major share of the profit and they finalize the deal either in their own favour or in favour of wholesalers. A study made by

Though they bear risk and provide form and time utility to the produce but they claim a good amount of margin and thus reduce the returns of the cultivators. Hence producers' share in consumers' money is very less in case of agricultural commodities. The majority of the markets present in agricultural sector are unregulated markets where prevalence of malpractices are rampant and this leads to lesser income to farmer producers. Indian farmers are not aware of the ruling prices of their produce prevailing in big markets. That is why, they have to accept any un-remunerative price for their produce as offered by traders or middlemen. There is lack of collective organization on the part of Indian farmers. A very small amount of marketable surplus is being brought to the markets by a huge number of small farmers leading to a high transportation cost. Lack of standardization and grading practices are rampant in India. Therefore, the farmers fail to fetch a good price of their quality produce. Inadequacy of institutional finance and credit force the farmers to lend money from local money lenders and traders. In turn the farmers are forced to sell their produce to those money lenders and traders in lesser price than the price prevailing in the market.

Suggestions for Improvement

State and union government should build proper cold storages, storages and warehouse facilities in adequate number across the country. Proper road, rail and air connectivity should be present to link these storage facilities. The elimination of mediators is necessary from agricultural marketing because unless the farmer is allowed the facility of direct sales to the customer, he cannot receive a fair price for it. Farmers should be encouraged to sell their produces at pan India online portals like e-NAM where there is no presence of middle men and the farmers can fetch fair remunerative price. Institutional credit facilities should be provided at farmers' doorsteps through banks, cooperative societies and SHGs so that the farmers need no to avail the services of local money lenders. This will reduce the distress sale and will increase producers' share in consumers' money. Farmers should be encouraged to participate in contract farming, cooperative farming and cooperative marketing as these will increase their bargaining power and in turn increase their income. Sufficient arrangements should be made for the transmission of the authorized prices of agricultural produce and quantity of production etc. so that the facts relating to agricultural marketing can be put before the concerned parties. Though the Agricultural Production Act was passed in 1937 for standardization of agricultural products, still no recognizable progress has been made in this direction. For making an effective system of expansion of the activity of gradation and quality control, laboratories should be established. A central laboratory was established in Nagpur and provisional laboratories were established in Madras, Kanpur, Rajkot, Amritsar, Calcutta, and Mumbai

but these should be situated in small villages and not in big towns. To provide a fair price to the farmers for their produce in the mandis, 'organized mandis' and regulated markets should be established by the government, appropriate arrangements should be made in these mandi-markets for weighting, storage, transport etc. and the farmers should also be given regularly powers in it. Last but not the least, farmers are to be trained properly by concerned authorities to better understand their market conditions as this, in long run, will help the farmers to fetch higher income.

References

1. Kumar, M. (2018) Problems of agriculture marketing in India. *Int. J. Res. Anal. Rev.(IJRAR)*, 5(4), 22-27.
2. Singh, M., & Kumar, R. (2006). Administration of Rural Agricultural Marketing: Need for Reforms. *Rural Development Administration in the 21st Century: A Multi- dimensional Study*, 264.